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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling Approaches: Book of Abstracts

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Assessment of the Bioprotective Capabilities of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Artisanal *Alheira*, a Portuguese Fermented Sausage

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Abstract

Alheira is a non-ready-to-eat fermented meat sausage traditional in Portugal, made with cooked poultry/pork meat, bread soaked in the meats' cooking broth and seasonings. The fermentation of this sausage occurs naturally, depending on batter colonization by populations of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) naturally present in the raw materials and in local environments. Aside from fermentation, these bacteria also produce bioactive molecules which aid in the inhibition of pathogens and in development of desirable organoleptic properties in the finished product.

The aim of this study was to isolate LAB present *alheira* sausages and evaluate their potential for application during manufacture as biopreservatives.

Sixty-four *alheiras* from 13 regional producers were analysed and 345 LAB were isolated from MRS and MI7 media and confirmed by Gram staining and catalase test. The antimicrobial activity of the isolates against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella* spp. at 37 °C was tested by spot-on-lawn assay. Sixty-three selected strains (43 from MRS, 20 from MI7) were further tested for their antimicrobial activity at 10 °C. Acidification capacity, lactic acid production and proteolytic activity was also determined. The suitability of the strains was evaluated by adjusting two separate Principal Component Analyses (PCA) on MRS and MI7 data.

For MRS strains, PCA explained 73% of data, with PC1 (39%) characterising strains with high acidification, PC2 (20%) was linked to strains with great antimicrobial activity at low temperature and PC3 (14%) allowed the differentiation between isolates with good proteolytic and lactic acid production. For MI7 strains, PC1 (44%) correlated with greater acidification, PC2 (20%) distinguished strains with higher acidification from isolates with good antimicrobial activity against *Salmonella* spp., and PC3 (12%) characterised strains with good inhibition of *S. aureus* at 10 °C. Finally, the PCA allowed the identification of several isolates with both good acidifying capacity and antimicrobial potential, desirable qualities in starter cultures for use in *alheira* production.

Keywords: Fermented sausage; biocontrol; pathogens; principal component analysis.

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